

EFFECTS OF THE CURE PRESSURE ON INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF CFRP-STEEL HYBRID LAMINATE CURED BY HOT PRESSING FOR A SHORT TIME

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1 Introduction

In recent years, researches on the application of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) of high specific stiffness and strength to various transportation vehicles have attracted much attention with the increasing requirements of energy saving vehicles and clean air environment. As a great progress, CFRP has been successfully applied to primary structures of airplanes, such as Airbus A380 and Boeing 787. In addition to CFRP, a kind of fiber metal laminate (FML) named Glare composed by glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) layers and Aluminum alloy layers (GFRP-Al hybrid laminate) has been successfully applied to the upper fuselage of A380 and CFRP-Al hybrid laminates has been developed for the application of primary structural elements[1,2]. Now, more and more researchers and automotive manufacturers are concerned with the application of CFRP to the mass-produced automobiles to reduce the weight of cars due to the rapid increase of the fuel prices and the increasing world-wide requirements of clean air environment [3,4]. On the other hand, the application of CFRP to automobiles must consider different requirements compared to aircraft applications. One of the requirements is about the fabrication cost. Much lower fabrication cost of structural elements than that of aircraft is very important for the application of CFRP to the automotive structure. It is difficult to apply the technologies of autoclave or even vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) to the automotive structures due to the long cure time and the high energy consumption. Therefore, in order to explore a new cure method within very short time

and with low energy consumption, the prepreg-based hot pressing for a short time comes into the front stage and several composite manufacturers have developed CFRP prepreps which can be cured by hot pressing for only several minutes[3,4]. Another requirement is relative to the adhesive strength between CFRP and metal. A proper adhesive strength to the CFRP-metal interface is required to effectively transfer the load between CFRP and metal for CFRP-metal joints or CFRP-metal hybrid structures. Many researches have been conducted to explore effective adhesive technologies[5,6]. In the new hot pressing cure technology for a short time, different cure pressures are recommended by different manufacturers. Thus, how to choose a proper cure pressure for the CFRP-steel hybrid laminates is not clarified.

In this paper, CFRP-steel hybrid laminate is focused on for the fabrication of lightweight automotive elements. The effects of the cure pressure on the interlaminar shear strength of CFRP-steel hybrid laminate cured by hot pressing for a short time are investigated by short beam test of three-point bend. Three cure pressures of 5MPa, 8MPa, 13MPa are investigated. Furthermore, repeated thermal shock tests (-40°C to 150°C) of 500 cycles are conducted for the hybrid laminates cured at different cure pressures. The interlaminar shear strength of the hybrid laminates after thermal shock test is investigated. Experimental results shows that cure pressure has significant effects on the interlaminar shear strength of hybrid laminates and the thermal shock also significantly affect the interlaminar shear strength of the hybrid laminates.

The hybrid laminates cured at 8MPa gives relatively higher interlaminar shear strength.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Materials and fabrication of specimens

The unidirectional CFRP prepreg TR50SR02E2 used in this research is provided by Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.. The thickness of the prepreg is 0.22mm, the cure temperature is 140°C for 10 minutes. The cure pressure is taken as a parameter and three pressures of 5MPa, 8MPa, and 13 MPa are investigated. The steel sheet SPFC590 of thickness in 0.5mm is employed as the metal layer. To simulate automotive structural elements, n-shape-like structures of $[0_8]$ /steel and $[0_8]$ /adhesive film/steel, as shown in Fig.1, are fabricated using a hot pressing machine at 140°C and three cure pressures as mentioned above for 10min.. The adhesive film DNP D2A120HR-S(P70) is provided by DNP (Dai Nippon Printing Co., Ltd.). The film consists of epoxy resin and a non-woven fabric cloth of PET (Polyethylen terephthalate), the thickness of the film is 127 micrometer, and the thickness of the PET cloth is 70 micrometer. The specimens for short beam test of three-point bend are cut from the central areas of the top face and the side face of the n-shape-like structure. The geometry of the specimen is 25.4mm in length, about 2.3mm in thickness, and 6.4mm in width referring to ASTM D

Fig. 1 CFRP-steel laminated element.

2344/D 2344M and JIS K 7078. All kinds of the specimens are listed in Table1. It is noted that every line has three types of specimens cured by three different pressures. The plasma spray technique is employed for the degreasing of the steel layer surface.

Table.1 List of specimens

Specimen type	Surface treatment	Adhesive film	Pressure (MPa)	Thermal shock	Cut from
A-5, 8, 13-top	degreasing	not	5, 8, 13	not	top face
A-5, 8, 13-side	degreasing	not	5, 8, 13	not	side face
A-5, 8, 13-thermal-top	degreasing	not	5, 8, 13	yes	top face
A-5, 8, 13-thermal-side	degreasing	not	5, 8, 13	yes	side face
B-5, 8, 13-top	degreasing	yes	5, 8, 13	not	top face
B-5, 8, 13-side	degreasing	yes	5, 8, 13	not	side face
B-5, 8, 13-thermal-top	degreasing	yes	5, 8, 13	yes	top face
B-5, 8, 13-thermal-side	degreasing	yes	5, 8, 13	yes	side face
C-5, 8, 13-top	not	yes	5, 8, 13	not	top face
C-5, 8, 13-side	not	yes	5, 8, 13	not	side face
C-5, 8, 13-thermal-top	not	yes	5, 8, 13	yes	top face
C-5, 8, 13-thermal-side	not	yes	5, 8, 13	yes	side face

2.2 Thermal shock testing

In addition to the cure pressure, it is also interested that how the extreme temperature condition affect the interlaminar shear strength of CFRP-metal hybrid laminates. For this purpose, repeated thermal shock tests from -40°C to 150°C, as shown in Fig. 2, are conducted for half of the specimens using a thermal shock chamber (ESPEC CORP TSA-201S-W). One cycle of the thermal shock test includes exposing the specimen in room temperature 20°C for 5min., next in 150°C for 30min., then in 20°C for 5min. again, and finally in -40°C for 30min. Total 500 cycles of thermal shock are conducted for the specimens.

Fig. 2 Diagram of the thermal shock cycle.

2.3 Cross-section analysis of specimens

Before the mechanical test for the investigation of the interlaminar shear strength of the specimens, the cross-sections of all kinds of the specimens are

analyzed using optical microscopic, the internal microstructure, and the variation of the thickness of the adhesive film as well as the specimen are investigated for the specimens experienced and not experienced thermal shock test.

2.4 Interlaminar shear strength testing

After the analysis of the cross-section of the specimens, three-point bend tests of short beam for all kinds of specimens are conducted to investigate the effects of the cure pressure, surface treatment, and thermal shock on the interlaminar shear strength of CFRP/steel hybrid laminate. Test setup is shown in Fig. 3 referring to JIS K 7078. The span is 12mm, the diameter of lower pin and upper pin are 3mm and 5mm, respectively. Bend tests are conducted using a MTS 810 material-testing system and the loading rate is 0.5mm/min. Three specimens are tested for each kind of specimens.

Fig. 3 Setup of three-point bend test.

3 Experimental results

Experimental results are presented in the following Fig. 4 to Fig. 12. Cross-section images of the specimen without the adhesive film, cured at 8MPa, and not experienced the thermal shock are presented in Fig. 4. The specimen is cut from central area of

Fig. 4 Images of the cross-section of the specimen without adhesive film and cured at 8MPa. a) Parallel to the fibers, b) perpendicular the fibers.

the top face of the n-shape-like structure. Similar images are observed from the specimens cut from the side face and those cured at 5MPa and 13MPa. It is noted that, no obvious variation can be observed on the cross-sections of the specimens without the adhesive film, cured at all three pressures, and after thermal shock cycles, although the images of the cross-section image are not given here. This fact reveals that thermal shock cycles do not induce obvious damage in the specimens without the

Fig. 5 Typical images of the cross-sections of the specimens with adhesive film and cured at 5MPa.

adhesive film. Typical images of the cross-sections of the specimens with an adhesive film, cured at 5MPa, and not experienced the thermal shock are presented in Fig. 5. No obvious damage can be observed from the cross-sections of the specimens. Perfect bonding is observed at the interface between the film and steel. The bonding interface between the film and CFRP is not as clear as the interface of the film and steel since partial material of the film is pressed into the CFRP layer. Similar images are observed from the specimens cured at 8MPa and 13MPa except that the thickness of the film decreases as the cure pressure increases. The details about the variation of the thickness of the film as well as the specimens will be given a little later.

Images of the specimens with adhesive film and after thermal shock are shown in Fig. 6 to Fig.8 for the specimens cured at three pressures, respectively. The surface of the steel layer is degraded using plasma spray technique. From these figures, multiple cracks occurred in the adhesive film are observed in the images of the cross-sections parallel to the fiber direction, especially in the specimens cut from the

Fig. 6 Images of the cross-sections of the specimens with adhesive film, cured at 5MPa, and after thermal shock.

Fig. 7 Images of the cross-sections of the specimens with adhesive film cured at 8MPa and after thermal shock.

Fig. 8 Images of the cross-sections of the specimens with adhesive film cured at 13MPa and after thermal shock.

top face. In the specimens cut from the side face, relatively few cracks are observed, except for the specimens cured at 13MPa. Most of the cracks occurred along the interface between the PET fiber of the fabric cloth and the surround resin. In contrast, damage is not observed from the CFRP layer. Compared to the images shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, it is recognized that these cracks are induced by the thermal shock cycles. These facts reveal that this kind of adhesive film can not be used in this extreme temperature environment because the fabric cloth of PET is usually used in the environment below 130 °C.

The thickness values of all specimens including those experienced thermal shock are depicted in Fig. 9 since the thermal shock test has not obvious influence on the thickness of the specimens. The data point represents the averaged value of three specimens experienced thermal shock and three ones not experienced thermal shock, and the scatter range

Fig. 9 Variations of the thickness of the specimens with or without adhesive film.

is less than 0.1mm. The thickness of the specimens cut from the top face decreases as the cure pressure increase. In contrast, the thickness of the specimens cut from the side face has slight change. The reason is that the interval between the punch and the die in the top face area is not controlled to be as the same as the interval in the side face area at the specified pressure during cure process. The thickness values of the adhesive film layers in the specimens with an adhesive film are depicted in Fig.10. The original film thickness is 127 micrometers, the thickness is reduced to about 60 micrometers after cure at 5MPa, and it continuously decrease as the pressure increases, except for one case of the specimens cut from the side face and after thermal shock. It is also observed that the thickness of the film layer has a recovery after thermal shock. This recovery is considered to be induced by the cracks occurred in the film layer during thermal shock test.

Fig. 10 Variations of the thickness of the adhesive film layer.

The results of short beam 3-point bend tests are presented in Fig. 11 to Fig. 13. Typical load-displacement curves of the specimens cut from the top face are depicted in Fig. 11. All the other specimens show the similar load-displacement curves. Significant decrease of the maximum value of the load is observed in the case of specimens with an adhesive film and experienced the thermal shock. The maximum load is used for the calculation of the interlaminar shear strength according to the following formulae.

$$\tau_{xy} = \frac{P \times E_{CFRP}}{(E_{steel}I_1 + E_{CFRP}I_2)} \frac{h_2}{4} (h_2 + 2h_1 - 2\eta) \quad (1)$$

$$I_1 = B \left[\frac{h_1^3}{12} + \frac{h_1}{4} (2\eta - h_1)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

Fig. 11 Load-displacement curves of various specimens.

$$I_2 = B \left[\frac{h_2^3}{12} + \frac{h_2}{4} (2h_1 + h_2 - 2\eta)^2 \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\eta = \frac{E_{steel} h_1^2 + E_{CFRP} (h_2^2 + 2h_1 h_2)}{2(E_{steel} h_1 + E_{CFRP} h_2)} \quad (4)$$

where P is the maximum value of the load, B is the width of the specimen, $E_{steel}=210\text{GPa}$ and $E_{CFRP}=126\text{GPa}$ are the Young's ratios of the steel and CFRP, h_1 and h_2 are the thickness values of the steel and CFRP, and η denotes the distance from the steel surface to the neutral axis of the hybrid laminated beam, respectively. Equations (1) to (4) are derived based on the classical beam theory. The results of the interlaminar shear strength for various specimens are given in Fig. 12 a) to d). In the plot a), the results of the specimens without the adhesive film are given. The shear strength increases as the cure pressure increases from 5MPa to 8MPa and then has slight variation as the cure pressure increases to 13MPa. In addition, after thermal shock (dash lines), the shear strength increases by about 8%. It is speculated that the thermal shock in the high temperature enhances the cure degree of the epoxy resin of the CFRP. There is a slight difference between the results of the specimens cut from the top face and the side face. The results of the specimens with an adhesive film and surface degreasing are shown in the plot b). In the case of the specimens not experienced thermal shock (solid

Fig. 12 Interlaminar shear strength of various specimens.

lines), the shear strength increases as the cure pressure increases and the strength are enhanced by about 11% compared to that of the specimens

without the adhesive film. After thermal shock, the shear strength of the specimens cut from the side face has slight variation. However, the interlaminar shear strength of the specimens cut from the top face decreases significantly as the cure pressure increases. The cracks induced by thermal shock and the decrease of the film thickness due to the increase of the cure pressure are considered to be the reasons that result in the decrease of the interlaminar shear strength. In the case of the specimens cut from the side face, the thickness of the adhesive film has slight variation, as shown in Fig. 10, and the cracks in the film are relatively small so that the interlaminar shear strength has slight change. In the plot c), similar results are observed for the specimens with an adhesive film but without applying surface treatment to the steel layer, except that the shear strength of the specimens cut from the top face, after thermal shock, and cured at 8MPa does not decrease. The reason for this result is not completely clarified and further tests are necessary since the scatter bar of the test results is longer than other cases.

4 Conclusions

The effects of cure pressure, surface treatment, adhesive film, and thermal shock on the interlaminar shear strength of CFRP-steel hybrid laminates are investigated experimentally. Following conclusions are obtained based on the present experimental results.

1. The cure pressure has significant influence on the interlaminar shear strength of the CFRP-steel hybrid laminate. A proper selection of the cure pressure is necessary to achieve proper strength at reasonable cost. From the present test results, 8MPa is considered to be the proper cure pressure.
2. Inserting an adhesive film between CFRP and steel enhances the interlaminar shear strength by about 8%. However, a proper election of the adhesive film depending on the operation environment of the hybrid laminated structures is important.
3. Thermal shock has significant influence on the interlaminar shear strength of the hybrid laminates with an adhesive film.
4. The control of the thickness of the adhesive film as well as the laminate is important to assure the

geometry and the mechanical properties of the hybrid laminate.

5. The degreasing surface treatment for the steel layer using plasma spray has slight influence on the interlaminar shear strength of the laminates with an adhesive film.

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